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IMPACT OF TIME FROM INJURY TO OPERATION ANTERIOR CRUCIATE LIGAMENT ON THE TEGNER SCOR

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Introduction.

The knee is one of the most complex joints in the human body and is frequently exposed to injuries. The purpose of this study was to investigate whether the time interval from anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) injury to surgery affects the Tegner Activity Score.

Methods

A total of 700 patients who underwent ACL reconstruction were evaluated. All participants completed the Tegner Activity Score questionnaire before and after surgery. Demographic data, sports activity level, and the intervals from injury to diagnosis and from injury to surgery were recorded.

Results

The study included 556 men (79.4%) and 144 women (20.6%) with a mean age of 27 years. Of these, 271 were professional athletes, 398 recreational athletes, and 31 non-athletes. The most common sport was football (47.1%), followed by basketball (16.4%), handball (10.1%), and martial arts (5.9%). The postoperative Tegner score showed a significant negative correlation with the time from injury to diagnosis ($\rho = -0.239$, $p < 0.001$) and the time from injury to surgery ($\rho = -0.348$, $p < 0.001$). Professional athletes achieved significantly higher postoperative Tegner scores than recreational athletes and non-athletes ($\chi^2(30) = 281.732$, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion

Longer delays from injury to diagnosis and surgery are associated with poorer postoperative functional outcomes as measured by the Tegner score. Professional athletes demonstrated superior recovery compared with recreational athletes and non-athletes. Early diagnosis and timely surgical intervention are essential for optimizing return-to-sport outcomes following ACL reconstruction.

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